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An Analysis of the Effects of Monetary and Non- Monetary Incentives on Performance Levels of Employees in Organisations: A Case of Mutare Polytechnic, January 2013 to December 2015

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An Analysis of the Effects of Monetary and Non-Monetary Incentives on Performance Levels of Employees in Organisations: A Case of Mutare Polytechnic, January 2013 to December 2015

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ABSTRACT

This study is an analysis of the effects of monetary and non monetary incentives on the performance levels of lecturers at Mutare Polytechnic covering the period of January 2013 to June 2015. The population size was comprised of 15 administrators and 220 lecturers at Mutare Polytechnic and a stratified and purposive sample of 31 were the respondents. A mixed method research approach which applied both the qualitative and quantitative approaches in a single study was used in the study. The research instrument was a questionnaire complemented by interviews in the collection of data. Empirical evidence and results revealed that “monetary and non monetary incentives impact on and can improve the lecturers’ performance levels. The study revealed many performance variables in the findings, and the strategies that can be used by Mutare Polytechnic to improve the performance levels of lecturers are detailed under researchers’ input/Recommendations section. The organisation must organize and set up a yearly calendar of trainings (workshops and seminars) for lecturers (staff) to train in such areas as Public Relations, Organisational Culture, Organisational Development, conditions of service, health and safety, to name a few. The researcher ultimately adopted the null hypothesis that monetary and non monetary incentives do improve the performance levels of lecturers at Mutare Polytechnic.

Keywords: incentives, factors, performance, polytechnic, administrators.

INTRODUCTION

Mutare Polytechnic is a government training institution which falls under the Ministry of Higher and Tertiary Education, Science and Technology Development. It is one of the seven polytechnics in Zimbabwe. The Principal is the head of the station and/or accounting officer reporting to the Permanent Secretary through the Director of Manpower Planning in the Ministry. Mutare Polytechnic hosts satellite centres and vocational training centres (VTCs) in Manicaland districts, such as Magamba, Marange, Rusitu, Nyanyadzi, Vengere centres. Its mandate (raison d’être) /reason for existence is to train people in various skills and competencies thereby contributing in building up human capital (HC) to facilitate national productivity. The main student catchment area is Manicaland but it also spills over to other provinces nationally and internationally (through bilateral protocols/arrangements) with other countries. Mutare Polytechnic is a typical matrix organisation which functions through (vide) the following five (5) divisions with 220 trainers/lecturing staff:

- Applied Arts and Hospitality Division
- Commerce Division
- Information Technology
- Engineering Division
 - o Automotive Engineering
 - o Electrical Engineering
 - o Mechanical Engineering
 - o Civil and Construction Engineering
- Research, Education and Enterprise Development Division.

Mutare Polytechnic churns out an average of 1600 graduates per year from both the January and May intakes from the various disciplines. These graduates are awarded National Certificates, National Diplomas and Higher National Diplomas, respectively. In addition, single subject certificates are offered at National Foundation Certificate level, especially by the VTCs. Parallel short courses of one year duration (six months theory and six months attachment) are also offered in all the above divisions and disciplines within those divisions. An average of 500 graduates pass through this alternative strategy which caters for those students/participants/trainees that may not possess the academic entry requirements for the mainstream National Certificate, National Diploma and Higher National Diploma courses. It is also important to highlight that the Polytechnic hosts a Bachelor of Technology degree programme in Wood Technology. Thus it goes without saying that the Polytechnic is shouldered with a very big and noble responsibility to discharge. This has motivated the researchers to examine in detail the effect of this one very important motivator of performance, namely "monetary and non monetary incentives." However, as a government institution, Mutare Polytechnic does not operate autonomously. It functions under the direction of the Minister. The employees (including lecturers) are governed by the Public Service Commission by virtue of the legal instrument called Statutory Instrument 1 of 2000 which embodies all the conditions of employment, including remuneration or incentives, if any. The system is underpinned by a performance appraisal or performance management system called Results Based Management (RBM). In addition, a production policy directive was introduced, which aims at recognizing extra effort/extra initiatives by computing a monetary incentive payable to the employees involved. To achieve its vision, mission and core values, Mutare Polytechnic relies mainly on its core labour who are the lecturers, but of course, acknowledging other support staff. Therefore, this research study is focusing on the effects of incentives on the performance levels of the core labourer - the lecturers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research followed a mixed method research approach which applied both the qualitative and quantitative approaches in a single study or case. The two approaches were used to complement each other to provide a complete analysis of the problem (Masood (2010)). The mixed methods approach was adopted because the quantitative approach on its own could not adequately explain factors for low academic performance in secondary schools neither could the qualitative design on its own do so. This approach enabled high integration of quantitative data collected through both open ended or close ended questionnaire and qualitative data gathered through in depth face to face interviews. According to Al-Nsour Marwan, (2012) it capitalizes on the complementary strengths of qualitative and quantitative methods and also it yields to a comprehensive research product. The target population was Mutare Polytechnic lecturers and administration from which a sample was purposively drawn. These purposively sampled respondents have been chosen on the basis of their possible possession as Creswell (2012) supports. The researcher first talked to the respondents on the purpose and procedure of data collection and obtained their informed consent. Only lecturers and administrators interested in participating in the research were involved in the research as Walliman (2008) directs. The researcher informed them that participation in the research was voluntary and one was free to withdraw one's participation if one changed one's mind at whatever stage of the research. The study population comprised of 15 Mutare polytechnic administrators, and 220 lecturers. Purposive sampling was used to select five administrators and 26 lecturers. Stratified sampling was used to determine the number of respondents (administrators and lecturers) who will participate in the research. The number of participants was limited to purposively sampled thirty one from both strata and Armstrong (2014) affirms this. The questionnaire was preferred as a data collection instrument because of its various advantages and its relevance to the quantitative and qualitative research. Considering the sensitivity of the topic under study the aspect of anonymity made the questionnaire the most suitable instrument for data collection. College administrators (Principal's office and HODs) and lecturers were interviewed, using the structured interview. The choice of administrators was ideal because of their influence in the control and welfare of the teaching staff members and also the lecturers who are the obvious victims of administrative decisions.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Data captured through the open ended and close ended questionnaire was presented using figures and tables while that sourced through interviews was presented in narrative as directed by Chuck and Schutt (2012). Data from interviews and questionnaires was then discussed in response to the research questions. The following themes were examined: Lecturer grades/levels, Years of service at Mutare Polytechnic, The organisations respect of and concern for lecturers needs, Factors that could increase employee and organisational performance, the relationship between employee incentives and individual and organisational performance and Recommendations to Mutare Polytechnic

Management of techniques to improve individual and organisational performance. The lecturer grades/levels are as shown in table 1 and figure 1 below:

Table 1: Lecturer grades/level

Variable- Grade/level of lecturer	Frequencies	Percentages
Lecturer	13	42
Senior lecturer	5	16
Principal lecturer	13	42
Total	31	100

Figure 1: Lecturer grades/level

The statistics above in table 1 and figure 1 on lecturer grades/levels depicts that the lowest level of lecturers is represented by 42% and the middle 16% and the highest level 42%.

Table 2: Years of service at Mutare Polytechnic

Variables	Frequency	Percentages
Years of service at Mutare Polytechnic		
Less than 5 years	5	16
5 – 10 years	14	45
Over 10 years	12	39
Total	31	100

Figure 2: Years of service at Mutare Polytechnic

This variable of “**years of service**” serves to measure the stability of tenure. Read in conjunction with seniority, it also depicts that tenure is positively correlated to seniority. Most of the principal lecturers have served for more than ten years.

1.1.1 Presentation and analysis of responses to questions in the questionnaire

The following questions were asked and the responses are recorded and analyzed here accordingly.

Table 3: Responses to questions in the questionnaire

Qn No	Variable	Yes		No		Total
		Freq	%	Freq	%	
5	Do monetary and non monetary incentives affect your performance at work?	29	94	2	6	100
6	Are you motivated by the incentive system of this organisation?	12	39	19	61	100
7	Do you get incentives e.g. monetary, food hampers, suits, uniforms, autonomy respect?	19	61	12	39	100
8	Are your working conditions favourable?	17	55	14	45	100
9	Do you feel secure as far as your career is concerned in this organisation?	16	52	15	48	100
10	Can you be motivated by participating in decision making?	28	90	3	10	100
11	Do you think being given the opportunity to use your ability in the work place can increase organisational performance and effectiveness	30	97	1	3	100
12	Does your job description instill a sense of challenge and achievement to you?	24	77	7	23	100
13	Do you feel motivated if you are rewarded for goal attainment?	29	94	2	6	100
14	If the organisation strives for strategies that motivate workers, would that contribute to an improvement to your performance?	30	97	1	3	100
15	Do you feel staff training, information availability and communication to lecturers has an impact on your performance level?	28	90	3	10	100
16	Do you feel that the Result Based Management (RBM) appraisal system is an effective measure of your performance?	15	48	16	52	100
17	Does the current management style/system inspire you to perform better?	15	48	16	52	100
18	Does the Ministry's production policy encourage you to perform better?	6	19	25	81	100
19	Does your performance as a lecturer/trainer determine the pass rate at the institution?	29	94	2	6	100
20	Do monetary and non monetary incentives improve your status or ego?	25	19	6	81	100

1.1.2 Interpretation of result findings and statistics in 4.1.5 above

The following interpretations of the above statistical data can be deduced:

- ❖ Responses to question 5 reveal that 94% of the respondents feel that monetary and non monetary incentives affect their performance at work.
- ❖ From question 6 and 7, 39% of the respondents feel motivated by the organisation's incentive system, while 61% claim that they do not get the incentives (which reveal a striking consistency of responses to both questions).
- ❖ Question 8 and 9 also reveal consistency and validity in that (Question 8) 55% of the respondents feel that the working conditions were./are favourable and a similarly 52% feel that their career is secure in the organisation (Question 9).
- ❖ Question 10 and 11 are checking on related motivational variables where (Question 10) 90% of respondents wish to participate in decision making and (Question 11) 97% feel that they and the organisation would perform both if innovation is encouraged.
- ❖ Responses to questions 12, 13 and 14 show that 77% feel that their jobs are challenging. 94% would like to be rewarded for their individual achievements and 97% of respondents would perform better if the organisation improves its motivational strategies.
- ❖ Question 15 – 90% of respondents feel that non monetary incentives such as staff training, availability of information and communication to lecturers would/does impact positively on their work performance levels.
- ❖ However (Question 16) 84% of the respondents questions the effectiveness and validity of the current Results Based Management (RBM) performance appraisal system.
- ❖ Question 17 – 52% of the respondents are not inspired by the present management style at Mutare Polytechnic whilst 81% are not encouraged by the Ministry's production policy (Question 18).
- ❖ Question 19 – 94% of the lecturers feel that their performance influences/determines the pass rate of students
- ❖ Question 20 – 81% feels that monetary and non monetary incentives improve their status and ego.

1.1.3 Written narrative section (Section B)

In section B of the researcher's questionnaire, respondents were asked to give written narratives, explanations, opinions and ideas pertaining to the following aspect:

- The organisations respect of and concern for lecturers needs (Q1)
- Explain the factors that they think could increase employee and organisational performance (Q2)
- Explain the relationship they see between employee incentives and individual and organisational performance (Q 3 and 4)
- Recommend to Mutare Polytechnic Management techniques to improve individual and organisational performance.

1.1.4 Findings from Section B

1.1.4.1 Organisation's respect of employees' needs and contributions of ideas

Three distinct categories of responses were recorded below in table 4.

Table 4: Respect of employees' needs and contributions

	Freq	%
Not respected/listened to/focused on	21	68
Partially respected/listened to/focused on	8	26
Yes, listened to and respected	2	6
Total	31	100

Therefore, 68% of respondents want their contributions and ideas to be respected and implemented.

1.1.4.2 Factors that could increase lecturers performance and organisational performance

Table 5: Factors that could increase lecturers performance.

	Freq
Provision of incentives, monetary and non monetary	17
Provision/availability of resources for work performance	8
Decision making/autonomy	6
Recognition and appreciation	5
Respect/listened to	4
Team work	3
Communication and feedback	3
Communication and feedback meetings	3
Restructuring of internal leadership e.g. HODs, Hods, LICs	3
No bootlicking, sellouts	2
Do internal training (seminars/workshops)	2
Qualification be respected and to determine seniority	1

The provision of incentives ranks highest in terms of factors that increase lecturers' and organisational performance (with 17 responses).

1.1.4.3 Correlation between incentives and performance: Explain the relationship between incentives and individual and organisation performance. (Q 3 and Q 4)

Table 5: Correlation between incentives and performance

	Freq	%
Incentives bring short bursts of individual performance	2	7
There is no significance because of long durations/ frequencies between payment of incentives	5	16
There is high positive correlation between incentives and individual lecturer's performance	18	58
No comments	6	19
Totals	31	100

Therefore, 58% of the respondents feel that there is a high positive correlation between incentives and individual lecturer's performance.

1.1.4.4 Respondents' recommendations/techniques to improve individual and organisational performance

Table 6: Respondents' recommendations to improve organisational performance

	Frequency
Provide monthly incentives (monetary and non monetary)	9
Communication and effective feedback	8
Provide training (workshops /seminars)	6
Celebrate achievements/awards/prizes/appreciation	6
Listen to respect and implement views	5
Provide adequate resources (including safety gear/technology	5
Joint involvement of management and lecturers in all activities at college	5
Decision making and autonomy	4
Encourage team work	4
Let staff tell their own stories	2
Create a conducive organisational environment	2
Do fair appraisals	1
Accountability for misdemeanors/punish culprits	1

The above shows the rank order of suggestions that must be implemented to improve the performance levels of lecturers, as given by respondents. Once again, incentives rank the highest on frequency.

CONCLUSIONS

- ❖ Mutare Polytechnic reviewed the modalities and implementation of the Ministry's production policy to ensure that it operates smoothly and equitably. This translated to significant positive performance levels of lecturers and Saks (2006) is in support of this.
- ❖ Mutare Polytechnic lecturers' participation in decision making is not followed and the participation of some lecturers is seen as a potential threat to the welfare of the organisation stifling of the development of new ideas/concepts and innovations.
- ❖ The RBM performance appraisal method is marred by those factors which are not the core duties of lecturers such as extra curricula or production activities in order for the appraisal to be fair, valid and focused on lecturer performance as McGregor and Cutcher-Gershenfeld (2006) endorses.
- ❖ The institution does not cushion commuting lecturer expenses, the institution does not arrange to ferry workers to and from work using its buses and covering certain routes or residential areas though the buses are available and mainly idle.
- ❖ There is no Information Centre which is open daily where all pertinent information on college activities, circulars, or announcements can be accessed by all so that no one remains in the dark about what is happening at Mutare Polytechnic.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- ❖ Mutare Polytechnic must organize and set up a yearly calendar of trainings (workshops and seminars) for lecturers (staff) to train in such areas as Public Relations, Organisational Culture, Organisational Development, conditions of service, health and safety, to name a few. These/such workshops will help to align/synchronize organisational goals and individuals goals to achieve goal congruence as Herzberg (1964) supports.
- ❖ The institution must celebrate achievements with all players/lecturers such as functions to celebrate trophies or awards from such activities as sports, trade fair, Manicaland Agricultural Show, symposia etc. This will build the spirit of solidarity and team work spirit.
- ❖ Mutare Polytechnic's management should arrange free meals or teas in the canteen for lectures on certain days of the week. This will demonstrate that management cares about the welfare of lecturers and this notion is supported by Kinicki/Kreitner, (2010).
- ❖ Access to college regalia must be done more transparently and some basic regalia such as T-shirts, identification cards should be issued to all free of charge.
- ❖ There should be an open system to enforce accountability for example if someone commits corruption, it should be punished and not condoned because corruption would spread and destroy the efforts of many well-meaning employees.
- ❖ The college must strive to provide adequate resources for work performance such as computers, teaching/lecturing aids, power, (generators), consumables, workshop equipment, transport and logistics in order not to frustrate zealous workers;
- ❖ Safety and protective gear must be provided to all according to the requirements of the job or work environment in order to optimize on performance and avoid or prevent accidents and injuries.

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